

Movie Recommendation System using Machine Learning

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Abstract— The recommendation system is a system which provides users with suggestions for certain resources such as books, movies, songs and other things according to some dataset. The recommendation system for movies predicts which movies would the user like based on attributes of the movies he likes or based on ratings of those movies. Such recommendation systems prove to be useful for organizations which maintain huge amounts of customer data and want to provide the best suggestions to the customers. The method used to achieve the above is collaborative-based filtering using the KNN algorithm. The system will recommend movies based on the threshold value of popularity of a specific movie. Popularity is the overall number of rates that a movie gets from the user. The coding is done using python programming language, while the two data sets considered are from Grouplens.org; where one has 9742 movies, and the other has 100836 rates.

Keywords—KNN, Movies, Ratings, Popularity Threshold, PivotTable, Machine learning, Recommenders

I. INTRODUCTION

Recommendation systems can be defined as a type of information filtering systems that try to predict the interests of users and make recommendations accordingly. Recommendation systems have many applications. These systems have gained much popularity in the past few years and are now employed by most of the online platforms we use. The content of these online platforms may consist of different things like movies, music, books, videos, friends, stories on social media websites, products on eCommerce websites, search results on Google. Generally speaking, these systems can collect data about a person's choices and use them to give better recommendations. The technique we would prefer to use for our project is collaborative-based filtering through the use of KNN(K nearest neighbour). Collaborative does not need the features of the items to be provided. Each user and each item is represented using feature vectors or embedding. It generates an embedding for both users and items. Item beds users and items in the same embedding space. Collaborative takes into consideration the opinion of other users when recommending items to a specific user. It takes note of items that a particular user likes and those that the similar liking users like.

The system gathers user feedbacks about various items and utilizes these for recommendations. Popularity threshold is considered a parameter that determines what films should be recommended to the users. In our case, we consider rating count of the particular film as a criterion to determine its popularity. Then we assume a certain minimal value to be the threshold of popularity. If the rating count exceeds the threshold of popularity, then the film may be recommended to the user; if it does not exceed the threshold, then the film will not be recommended to the user. Thus, the use of popularity threshold as the technique for movie recommendation is used to filter out unpopular films by their ratings. And if the particular film has enough popularity to be mentioned in recommendations, then its rating is placed into a pivot table. Every particular movie is given a rating by any number of users. Suppose user 1 provides a rating to any movie, then it gets reflected accordingly in the pivot table. The column of those users who haven't rated the movie will be provided null value. This way, the pivot table gives us exact data of each movie and user, which can then be converted to array matrix. On the basis of this data, we calculate Euclidean distance of KNN algorithm and further cluster all the nearest neighbours. Movies are clustered using the brute algorithm method, where there is a calculation of the similarity scores through the cosine angle of two vectors. Ultimately, we get grouped similar percentage of movies for recommendations. Hence, when a user watches a particular movie, he gets recommended other movies from the same group. Thus, the movies are filtered on the basis of their ratings and users having similar ratings. Thus, it proves an excellent method of recommendation.

II. RELATEDWORK

[1] proposed a technique using trust factor extracted with help of ratings given so that quality can be improved and better predictions can be done. A novel technique has been proposed for recommender system using film-trust dataset and its effectiveness has been justified with the help of experiments. Traditional recommender systems consider that all the users are independent and identical, its an assumption which leads to a total ignorance of social interactions and trust among user. Trust relation among users ease the work of recommender systems to produce better quality of recommendations.

[2] designed and implement a movie recommendation system. There are different genres, cultures and languages to choose from in the world of movies. Such a system can suggest a set of movies to users based on their interest, or the popularities of the movies. On an average of one year movie survey 600 movies are released in Hollywood. For streaming movie services like Netflix, recommendation systems are essential for helping users find new movies to enjoy. So far, a decent number of works has been done in this field. But there is always room for renovation.

[3] suggest a movie recommender system based on new similarity metric of users and opinion mining. The main aim of this paper is to find out what kind of opinion (negative, positive, or neutral) is there for movies and to provide top-k recommendation list for movies. This work also recommends reviews to use according to user similarity and rating pattern. Finally, validation of this movie recommendation system under various evaluation criteria has been done and results show that proposed system provides better result than traditional systems. [4] discussed about movie recommendation and the available method used for this purpose is collaborative filtering method. Within the collaborative filtering methods, matrix factorization

In [5], a novel recommendation algorithm based on Back Propagation (BP) neural network with Attention Mechanism (BPAM) is proposed. Specifically, BP neural network can be used to learn the complex relations between the target users and their neighbors. Different from the deep neural network, the shallow neural network, which means BP neural network, not only decreases the computational and storage resources but also avoids the problem of overfitting. Furthermore, an attention mechanism is also designed for capturing the global effect on all nearest target users of each user.

III. DATASET AND FEATURES

Collaborative filtering is commonly used in many recommendation systems. The data sets utilized in this research come from "GroupLens". Data have been collected from September 1997 to October 2018. Our recommendation system needs two datasets. The dataset of movies includes about 9742 movies with movie data and titles as the attributes of the columns. On the other hand, the next dataset, i.e., reviews dataset, consists of around 100,836 user reviews.

IV METHOD

Figure 1. Overall concept

Collaborative Filtering: This filtration approach is based on the fusion of the behavior of the user and then contrasting it with the behaviors of other users in the database. The history of all the users becomes an important element here. The key difference of the collaborative filtering from the content-based filtering is that, in the former case, the interaction of all users with the items determines the recommendation algorithm, while in the latter case, data of only the user in question is considered. There are two such approaches but effectively there is a one key idea behind the collaborative filtering.

There are two types of collaborative filtering algorithms:

- User-Based Collaborative Filtering

The fundamental principle behind this algorithm is to find users who have similar preference patterns as compared to the user 'A' and then recommend him items that were liked by similar users which he has not explored yet. This can be done by constructing an Item-User Matrix where all the ratings/viewed/liked items per user are taken into consideration and then their similarity is computed on the basis of which relevant recommendations will be made.

- For instance, if user 'A' likes 'Batman Begins', 'Justice League' and 'The Avengers' and similarly, the user 'B' likes 'Batman Begins', 'Justice League' and 'Thor' then both of them are having a similar interest because it is evident that these movies belong to the same genre i.e., Super-Heroes genre. Thus, there exists a possibility that the user 'A' will like 'Thor' and the user 'B' will like 'The Avengers'.

Disadvantages:

- People are fickle-minded i.e. their taste changes from time to time and as this algorithm is based on user similarity, it may pick up initial similarity patterns between 2 users who after sometime may have different preferences.
- There are many more users than items and therefore it becomes very difficult to maintain such large matrices and therefore needs to be recomputed very regularly.
- This algorithm is very susceptible to shilling attacks where fake users profiles consisting of biased preference patterns are used to manipulate key decisions.

- Item-based Collaborative Filtering

The concept in this case is to find similar movies instead of similar users and then recommending similar movies to that 'A' has had in his/her past preferences. This is done by finding every pair of items which were rated/viewed/liked/clicked by the same user, measuring the similarities of those rated/viewed/liked/clicked by all users who have both rated/viewed/liked/clicked both and finally recommending them on basis of similarity scores.

- Here, for example, we take 2 movies 'A' and 'B' and check the ratings of these movies by all the users who have rated both the movies and based on the rating similarity by users who have rated both and find similar movies. So for most common users who derated 'A' and 'B' both similarly and it is highly probable that 'A' and 'B' are similar. Therefore if someone has watched and liked 'A' they should be recommended 'B' and vice versa. Advantages over User-based Collaborative Filtering

- Unlike people's taste, movies don't change.
- There are usually a lot fewer items than people, therefore easier to maintain and compute the matrices.
- Shilling attacks are much harder because items cannot be faked

III. VISUALIZATION

Figure 2 illustrates the various visualizations.

Figure 2 Live visualizations

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To evaluate the performance of the proposed system, we conducted experiments on movie datasets with Google Collab. The proposed system will randomly take an input for a specific movie id and accordingly the pivot table will be formed. The attributes of the pivot table will be the movie id , ratings and the user id.

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Recommendations for Waterworld (1995):
1: Outbreak (1995), with distance of 0.3990267515182495:
2: True Lies (1994), with distance of 0.41963857412338257:
3: Stargate (1994), with distance of 0.43197691440582275:
4: Braveheart (1995), with distance of 0.4486045837402344:
5: Batman Forever (1995), with distance of 0.4569993019104004:

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VI Conclusion

The proposed recommendation system shall be very useful in practical deployment. Especially the excellent results observed in the top k recommenders is suggestive of the strong potential of proposed system for real world use. However, certain challenges do exist. The foundational data used to train the model may lead to inherent bias in the judgments. Hence in future it is proposed to build models on a wide range of datasets in order to reduce the bias and enhance the generalization. Proposed system can be deployed to infer present mental state of health from preferred choices of movies, thus serving as strong application in healthcare [6-9]. Also, the strong correlation between movie choices and user's personality [10-12] is worth investigating.

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